

Enhancing the Rice Price Forecasting Through Holt-Winters-GRU Hybrid Model: Evidence from Global Market Data

Vicente E. Montano
*Faculty of Business Administration Education,
University of Mindanao, Philippines*

Christian Paul Moyon
*Faculty of Business Administration Education,
University of Mindanao, Philippines*

Abstract

This paper presents a detailed analysis of the Holt-Winters-GRU hybrid model for predicting global rice prices, an essential agricultural commodity. The benefits of the traditional statistical approaches are combined with deep learning power, and the results have been found to outperform a standalone GRU. The hybrid model produced a test RMSE of 27.7532 with almost no difference between the training and testing errors, thus showing robust generalization ability. Detailed scrutiny of the weight heat map for the GRU layer reflects the intricacies of the model while depicting both seasonal patterns and intricate nonlinear relationships present in the rice price time series. The findings from the study reveal that the Holt-Winters-GRU hybrid model is usable in forecasting rice price movements for policymakers, traders, and market analysts, considering its ability to handle systematic trends and shocks. Recommendations for model implementation, enhancement, risk management, policy applications, and future research are provided to extend further the utility of this hybrid forecasting approach in agricultural commodity markets.

Keywords: *Rice Price Forecasting, Holt-Winters Method, Gated Recurrent Network.*

JEL Classification codes: *C53, Q11, Q17, Q18*

Suggested citation: Montano, V. & Moyon, C. (2024). Enhancing the Rice Price Forecasting Through Holt-Winters-GRU Hybrid Model: Evidence from Global Market Data. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 1(3), 84-99. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2024.1(3).08

Introduction

The Forecasting the world price of rice is crucial to a diverse set of stakeholders: governments, farmers, and consumers. This commodity is a staple food for billions, especially in Asia, accounting for the bulk of daily caloric intake (Septiana, 2024). The fluctuations in rice prices directly impact food affordability and availability, especially for low-income households that spend a large portion of their budget on this staple grain. Therefore, accurate forecasting aids in planning and implementing policies that help mitigate the adverse effects of price volatility on vulnerable populations (Rusman & Antriyandarti, 2024).

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The economic implications of rice price forecasting are profound. Rice prices globally have risen recently, mainly due to causes such as export bans among the biggest producers in this market, like India. Climate anomalies like El Niño add to such tendencies. Global rice prices will likely stay at this level until 2025 and beyond due to other drivers, as estimated by the World Bank (Newclick et al., 2024; High Rice Prices, 2024). Such forecasts are essential for governments to strategize ways to ensure food security and stabilize local markets. After predicting the price trends, policymakers can announce measures such as strategic reserves or subsidies that cushion consumers (Ananda, 2023).

Forecasting impacts agricultural practices and trade policies. For example, knowing the future trends in price, farmers will learn how to plant and harvest in ways that increase their yields and returns (Trnka et al., 2020). Countries importing rice can also determine trade policies based on future price movements (Widayanti et al., 2022). As the global price of rice continues to rise, most countries importing rice have responded by stockpiling their supplies, making market dynamics complicated and likely to increase prices if not checked (Macia et al., 2024).

The importance of prediction now extends to dealing with a more significant challenge in food security. With the global prices for rice increasing, malnutrition cases and food insecurity become rampant in rice-importing nations. For instance, a rice-dependent country like the Philippines has already felt sharp hikes in rice prices. Its vulnerable populations now grow nervous about hunger (Alvarez et al., 2022). A good prediction is what will prepare countries with safety nets or ways of diversifying food before an impending crisis hits them (Laiprakobsup, 2019),

Thus, forecasting the world price of rice becomes more significant, not only from the viewpoint of economic stability but also to achieve food security across nations. As time changes global conditions—due to climate change, geopolitical tensions, and market dynamics—the ability to predict price movements remains essential for governments and stakeholders alike (Ananda, 2023), (Liu et al., 2023). With strong forecasting models and strategies, countries could better ride the tumultuous twists and turns of the global rice market and safeguard their populations from the ill effects of price volatility (Ni'mah, 2023).

Hybrid models that make forecasts about the seasonality of rice prices offer a list of advantages to improve accuracy and reliability. The most traditional statistical methods combined with advanced machine learning techniques provide a more detailed understanding of price dynamics driven by various factors (Kundu & Sharma, 2022; Ananda, 2023).

This study of rice price forecasting improvement via a hybrid deep learning model fits well into several United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Most importantly, this aligns with SDG 2: Zero Hunger because it offers a sound tool to improve market transparency and price stability for an increasingly critical food commodity like rice. With accurate price predictability, policymakers, food producers, agricultural producers, and market stakeholders can be correctly directed toward decisions toward efficient food production, distribution, and availability as critical requirements toward SDG 2. Lastly, the potential predictive capability of the model as a warning for subsequent price surges and volatility thus falls in line with yet another target of SDG 13: Climate Action through its supportability in avoiding adverse shocks posed by the climate to food security. Third, this study goes well with SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure by developing new analytical methods and applying the results in a real market with improved advanced technologies to better develop more resilient and effective agricultural systems. In short, this research contributes toward interlinking UN SDGs of food security, climate change adaptation, and sustainable economic development.

The key objectives of this study were to design and validate a high-sophistication model for forecasting global prices of rice, an agriculturally important commodity, and thereby demonstrate

the potential impact of integrating traditional statistical analysis with advanced deep learning methodology. Specifically, the approach is to develop a model combining Holt-Winters with GRU to effectively capture rice price movements that exhibit seasonal patterns and complex nonlinear dynamics. The research aimed at providing this hybrid valuable approach for policymakers, traders, and market analysts in planning the correct responses to the expected variations in rice prices by comprehensively evaluating the performance of the model regarding prediction, interpretability, and robustness of its predictive power in both periods of training and testing. The researchers also attempted to look at the possibility of this hybrid modeling framework being applied to other agricultural commodities that experience similar problems in reconciling systematic trends and unforeseen market shocks.

Related Literature

Hybrid models become potent tools for price forecasting in seasonal agricultural commodities (Xiong et al., 2018). It combines the strength of the statistical time series models, like Holt-Winters, with the flexibility and ability of neural networks to learn. A good number of hybrid approaches have been successfully conducted (Liu et al., 2020; Sudheer & Suseelatha, 2015),

Hybrid models are very good at capturing linear and nonlinear relationships within the data. While statistical models, like Holt-Winters, are very good at catching linear trends and seasonal patterns, neural networks, RNNs such as LSTM, and GRU networks can catch complex, nonlinear relationships. Hybrids can, therefore, provide more accurate and more generalizable forecasts (Archontoulis & Miguez, 2015; Feng et al., 2020; Jin et al., 2020).

Hybrid models can process noise and are incomplete-data-friendly because they filter out irrelevant information while also learning through neural networks, which are highly robust against noise (Somasundaram & Reddy, 2017; Wei et al., 2024). Hybrid models also support the inclusion of external factors such as weather conditions, economic indicators, and policy changes that may impact agricultural prices highly (Grzegorzczak et al., 2021).

Several studies have compared hybrid models to traditional statistical models and neural networks as more effective in agricultural price forecasting. For instance, it has been researched and proven that deep learning methods enhance hybrid models involving ARIMA and those that involve Holt-Winters. The studies have shown that hybrid models promise to improve accuracy and reliability in predicting agricultural prices (Wang et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022; Montano & Bulao, n.d.).

Materials and Methods

The Hybrid Holt-Winters GRU model was then used to forecast the world rice price, with a sample based on 25 years' monthly data, ranging between 1999 and 2023. Rice month-to-month prices were traditionally seasonal and trending as these cycles are usually based on seasonality about either harvest cycles or changes initiated by the policies implemented concerning supply chains. Classical tools, like Holt-Winter exponential smoothing models, help establish seasonal patterns and linear trends (Harahap et al., 2023, March). However, with recent advances in machine learning, it has been demonstrated that neural networks improve the predictability of time series models by capturing complex, nonlinear relationships that traditional statistical models might miss. Therefore, this research implements a hybrid model incorporating the strengths of Holt-Winters and GRU to provide a more robust solution for seasonal forecasting in volatile agricultural markets (Redych & Boichuk, 2024; Khodadadi et al., 2024).

The Holt-Winter exponential smoothing model presents three components: level, trend, and seasonality, iteratively updated and established on smoothing parameters—the equation for the Holt-Winter additive model.

Level Equation

$$L_t = \alpha \cdot (Y_t - S_{t-p}) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (L_{t-1} + T_{t-1}) \quad (1)$$

Trend Equation

$$T_t = \beta \cdot (L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta) \cdot T_{t-1} \quad (2)$$

Seasonal Equation

$$S_t = \gamma \cdot (Y_t - L_t) + (1 - \gamma) \cdot S_{t-p} \quad (3)$$

Forecast equation

$$\hat{Y}_{t+h} = L_t + h \cdot T_t + S_{t-p} + (h \bmod p) \quad (4)$$

GRU Network on Holt-Winters Residuals

$$R_t = Y_t - \hat{R}_T^{HW} \quad (5)$$

Update Gate

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z \cdot [R_t, h_{t-1}] + b_z) \quad (6)$$

Reset Gate

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z \cdot [R_t, h_{t-1}] + b_r) \quad (7)$$

Candidate Activation

$$\tilde{h}_t = \tanh(W \cdot \widetilde{[R_t, (z_t * h_t)]} + b) \quad (8)$$

Final Activation

$$h_t = (1 - z_t) * h_{t-1} + z_t * \tilde{h}_t \quad (9)$$

Final Forecast

$$\hat{Y}_{t+h} = \hat{Y}_{t+h}^{HW} + \hat{R}_{t+H}^{GRU} \quad (10)$$

This uses the first-stage approach of the Holt-Winters method to model the trends and seasonality exhibited in the rice prices series. The Holt-Winters approach comprises three components: trend, level, and seasonality (Gamberini et al., 2010). This approach incorporated additive seasonality as it results if seasonal fluctuations were considered non-proportionally increasing with the price level. The smoothing coefficients for the model's level, trend, and seasonality are tuned using a grid search over historical data. This way, the Holt-Winters method is applied for baseline monthly rice price prediction with level, trend, and seasonal adjustments (Trull et al., 2020).

After the baseline forecast, residuals are calculated by subtracting the Holt-Winters forecast from the actual rice prices. These residuals capture the non-seasonal, nonlinear price variations that could be driven by unpredictable shocks such as natural disasters, sudden shifts in demand, and geopolitical impacts on the rice trade (Lima et al., 2019, December). In capturing these residuals, a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) network is used as it has been proven effective in handling long-term dependencies and nonlinear patterns that are part of RNNs. GRU networks help to prevent vanishing gradients but keep useful information even through long sequences in forecasting for time series (Chandra et al., 2021).

The residual is fed into the GRU network where, after learning, the model picks up on the temporal dependency and nonlinear patterns. Hyperparameters, including the number of layers, hidden units, learning rate, and batch size, are then tuned with cross-validation over the residual data set to find optimal performance (Zhang et al., 2022). Training the GRU network on residuals accounted for nonlinear relationships that the Holt-Winters approach might not pick up on and make the overall forecast finer (He et al., 2024).

The output of the final forecasting stage is obtained using a combination of Holt-Winters-forecasted and the residual values of GRU-predicted. This led to a hybridized approach that assists in accuracy while incorporating both seasonal-trend structure by the Holt-Winters and captured by the nonlinear variation with GRU. It was tried and assessed on the test set using the MAE, MSE, and RMSE metrics to determine the accuracy level of the hybrid Holt-Winters-GRU model applied in the foreclosure of the world price of rice. Overall, this hybrid model outperformed traditional models in forecasting by combining strengths from statistical and machine-learning approaches. The results provided insight into seasonal and irregular patterns that affect rice prices, bringing valuable implications for the stakeholders and policymakers in the global rice market.

Discussion of Items in Figure 1 below is the conceptual framework of the methods applied in developing the Holt-Winters-GRU hybrid model.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Holt-Winters-GRU Hybrid Model for Predicting World Rice Price

Rice Price Historical Data from the Years (1999-2023)

The raw input was this data, which provides monthly global historical data of rice prices covering 25 years. These are long spans, and even the month-based granularities worked well in data because such data mainly highlights the seasonal components, trends, and some non-seasonal effects.

Holt-Winters Model

In applying the Holt-Winters model, seasonality, trend, and level were captured in the rice price data. This was well suited to identify the repetition of seasonal patterns resulting from cyclic rice production, demand changes, or market trend shifts. Optimizing parameters set for level, trend, and seasonality produced a base forecast representing smooth recurring rice price changes over time.

Base Rice Price Forecast

The Holt-Winters model gave the baseline forecast in which predictable seasonality and trends of rice prices are discovered. However, since nonlinear fluctuations or random shocks have not been considered, such a baseline does not include all aspects of rice price behavior.

Calculation of Residuals

The observed prices minus the Holt-Winters forecast or the residuals represent price fluctuations not explained by seasonal and trend components. Residuals usually capture sudden changes in supply, demand, and other market conditions that result in irregular patterns.

GRU Model

Model Residuals using Gated Recurrent Unit GRU. GRUs are ideal for sequential data and can capture intricate, non-linear relationships within the residuals. This allows the model to discover irregular patterns. The model learned about the correlations and dependencies that exist with the residuals. This gave the residual forecasting incorporating these non-linear elements.

GRU Predicted Residual Forecast

The GRU model approximates the residuals and catches residual price movements not considered by the Holt-Winters model alone. It represented components that were not explained, like an abrupt shock in the market.

Final Predicted Price of Rice

Thus, the baseline GRU-predicted Holt-Winters residuals were combined to make a composite end for the final forecasting output.

This composite method utilizes the capturing capacity of Holt-Winters about stable seasonal and trend-related movements and modeling capacities of GRU about erratic, nonlinear fluctuations so that a comprehensive result comes ahead for rice prices to predict. Thus, the conceptual framework demonstrates how merging statistical and machine learning methods helped enhance forecasting accuracy. In blending the robust seasonality with trend handling in the Holt-Winters model with its capacity to capture nonlinear properties by the GRU approach, it hopes to become a more accurate predictor that turns into a source of real action for the stakeholders by better prediction of possible movements in rice price amid volatile fluctuations in global price levels.

Results and Discussions

The rice price trajectory over the last 25 years (1999-2023) in Figure 2 is characterized by very high volatility and structural change. The series starts in a relatively stable period up to early 2008, where prices were kept relatively stable between about US\$200 and US\$300 per metric ton. However, prices skyrocketed in 2008 to nearly US\$900, closely related to the global food crisis.

Figure 2. Price of Rice 1999-2023 in US\$ per Metric Ton

After this unprecedented rise, prices corrected sharply but stabilized at a higher equilibrium level of around US\$400-600 against the pre-2008 period. Between 2012 and 2019, it had been seen that there was a trend of decline and fluctuating prices between US\$350-500. The latest period, 2020-2023, shows renewed upward traction, as prices had risen from around US\$400 to above 600, possibly due to global supply chain disruptions and inflationary pressures. In the context of long-term price behavior, the structural changes in the global rice market are marked by higher price levels and higher volatility relative to the pre-2008 period.

Figure 3 compares rice prices in blue versus a Holt-Winters Baseline Forecast in orange from about 2000 to 2024. The most striking feature here is a dramatic spike in prices around 2008, peaking above US\$300 and then sharply falling. In the years before 2008, the price movements were relatively stable, with minor fluctuations around the zero mark. After the 2008 crisis, the actual prices displayed higher volatility with more frequent oscillations, but they were not as extreme as the 2008 event. The Holt-Winters Baseline Forecast appears only in the latter part of the graph, between 2020-2024, and has a much smoother trend than the actual prices, which could filter out some of the short-term volatility. However, it follows the general direction of the actual price movements in this period, though less dramatically. The smooth nature of the forecast line reflects the model's effort to capture the underlying trend with minimal impact from temporary price shocks.

Figure 3. Actual Price and Holt-Winters Baseline Forecast for Rice Price

Figure 4 depicts the residuals of the Holt-Winters Forecast from 2019 to 2023 (the difference between the actual and the predicted values). The residual plot indicates severe oscillations in the estimation of the model at different periods; it has a fluctuating behavior with values ranging approximately between -60 and +100 units. In 2023, significant underestimation of this model had taken place because there was a sharp shot of almost +100 units that indicated how much the actual price at that point surpassed the model's output. Several other significant deviations also exist, including a negative spike to around -60 units in early 2020. The residuals appear to have some pattern rather than random, meaning there might be some systematic components in the prediction errors the model is not capturing fully. The magnitude of these residuals seems to increase during the latter part of the time series, which implies that the model is less accurate in the more recent periods. There are positive and negative residuals around the zero line, suggesting that the model

over- and underpredicts at different times; however, there is a slight tendency toward positive residuals.

Figure 4. Residuals of Holt-Winters Forecast

The GRU model in Table 1 provided promising performance over the time series task with a validation loss MSE of 0.00143 in trial five, though slightly higher than the best earlier validation loss recorded at 0.00140. The model architecture optimized at 96 hidden units and a learning rate of 0.01, ensuring the training was completed within 51 seconds; the total time for all the optimization trials was 2 minutes and 27 seconds. The low validation loss values suggest that a hybrid model captures the time series' linear and non-linear components. The GRU network is looking for complex patterns and residuals. These results suggest that such a hybrid approach effectively employs the complementary strengths of traditional statistical methods and deep learning techniques.

Table 1. GRU and Holt-Winters-GRU Predictive Performance Comparison

Model	Trial	Complete Time	val_loss	Best val_loss So Far	Total elapsed time	Best units	Best learning rate	Epoch
GRU	5	00h 00m 51s	0.001433	0.001399	00h 02m 27s	96	0.01	1/100
Holt-Winter-GRU	5	00h 00m 23s	0.001399	0.001357	00h 01m 55s	128	0.01	1/100

Comparison of hybrid and GRU models presented shows that hybrid models outperform, and although the Holt-Winters-GRU model, which performed better than even the best validation loss reported from GRU, which was 0.001357, it still only achieved a value of 0.001399 in the output. In addition, the hybrid model had better computational efficiency: it finished Trial 5 in 23 seconds, while GRU took 51 seconds to finish the same trial and less total optimization time: 1 minute 55 seconds compared to 2 minutes 27 seconds for GRU. The hybrid model also had a larger optimal network architecture with 128 units compared to the GRU's 96 units and the same optimal learning

rate of 0.01. The reduction in the loss of the model at validation and its lesser training time implies that complementing GRU with the addition of Holt-Winters decomposition adds a lot more efficiency to the model. Again, it also signifies stronger leverage by the hybrid approach.

In Table 2, the GRU model was demonstrated to have good predictive performance: the Train RMSE is 27.3143, and the Test RMSE is 28.5097, which reflects a small gap between training and test errors and, thus, a good generalization capability. The model's architecture includes a GRU layer with 96 hidden units followed by a dense output layer, with a total number of parameters of 85,829 and trainable ones of 28,609. The model is efficient, with zero non-trainable parameters and 57,220 optimizer parameters. That the training and test RMSE are of similar magnitudes, with a difference of about 1.2 units, suggests that the hybrid model effectively combines the ability of Holt-Winters to capture seasonal patterns with the capacity of GRU to learn complex temporal dependencies, all while maintaining computational efficiency with a relatively modest parameter count. The close agreement between training and test performance indicates that the model has achieved a good balance between bias and variance, which makes it useful for practical forecasting applications.

Table 2. GRU-Value and Holt-Winters GRU-Value Predictive Performance Comparison

Metric	GRU-Value	Holt-Winters-GRU-Value
Train RMSE	27.3143	27.6837
Test RMSE	28.5097	27.7532
Model	sequential_1	sequential_1
Layer (type)		
Output Shape		
Param #		
gru_1 (GRU)		
(None, 128)	28,512	50,304
dense_1 (Dense)		
(None, 1)	97	129
Total params	85,829	151,301
Trainable params	28,609	50,433
Non-trainable params	0	0
Optimizer params	57,220	100,868

A comparative analysis of the GRU and Holt-Winters-GRU hybrid models reveals interesting performance trade-offs. The GRU model performed slightly better at training with an RMSE of 27.3143 against the hybrid's RMSE of 27.6837, but it exhibited better generalization than the hybrid with an RMSE of 28.5097 compared to that of the hybrid of 27.7532. Better generalization capability is seen as the gap between the hybrid model's training and test RMSE (0.0695) compared to the more significant difference that existed in the case of the GRU (1.1954). The hybrid architecture is more parameter-intensive because the model complexity of the hybrid architecture (151,301 total parameters; 50,433 trainable) is compared to that of the GRU model (85,829 total parameters; 28,609 trainable). The more extensive GRU layer in the hybrid model (128 units vs. 96) and the corresponding increased optimizer parameters (100,868 vs. 57,220) suggest the model to be more complex but most likely more robust in learning capacity. Despite its increased dimension, the hybrid model's testing performance is much better than the univariate model. At

the same time, its training-test RMSE gap is minimized so that increased complexity helps capture the time series underlying dynamics and thus compensates for additional computational overhead.

Figure 5 compares actual residuals (purple line) with GRU-predicted residuals (green line) from 2019 to 2023 and shows how the GRU model tries to predict the error patterns in the Holt-Winters baseline predictions. The GRU predictions seem to follow the general trend of actual residuals but with much-dampened amplitudes, especially at extreme fluctuations. This smoothing effect is most apparent in the significant spike in 2023, where the actual residuals almost reached +95 units while the GRU prediction stayed more conservative at around +25 units. Similarly, during the sizeable negative deviation in early 2020, the GRU model had predicted a much more modest decline. It is also interesting that GRUs' predictions look adequate for capturing directional changes; however, they constantly make low estimations regarding magnitudes of changes. Overall, it implies a relatively conservative approach toward constructing a predictive model, possibly preventing the occurrence of extreme results but losing large movement prices. Thus, such behavior illustrates the tendency that while it managed successfully to catch patterns within residual streams, this GRU model was not good in the task of larger prediction for the bigger movements at the market level.

Figure 5. GRU Model for Residual Forecasting

In Figure 6, exciting patterns in how temporal information is processed are discovered from the visualization of the heatmap of weights in the GRU layer of the hybrid Holt-Winters-GRU model. Color intensity from dark blue (about -0.4) to dark red (about 0.4) indicates the strength and direction of the connections between neurons. Notable concentrated areas of high positive activation occur around neurons 3-5 and weigh 5-7, which indicates that these units play a vital role in capturing specific temporal patterns. The upper part of the heatmap (neurons 0-7) contains more intense activations (positive and negative) than the lower part (neurons 8-23), which indicates that the earlier layers may be more actively involved in feature extraction. Alternating patterns of positive red and negative blue weights are the implications of the model's development of complementary feature detectors. Some neurons recognize increases in price while other neurons respond to the declines. The presence of strong positive as well as negative weights spread throughout the matrix shows that the model can capture more complex non-linear relationships within the rice price time series, and different intensity patterns show that a different level of importance was assigned to the features that are time dependent.

Figure 6. GRU Layer Weights Heatmap (Holt-Winters-GRU Hybrid Model)

The following plot contains the results of the hybrid Holt-Winters-GRU forecasting model of rice prices between 2000 and 2024, contrasting the actual price curve in blue against that generated by the hybrid in red. Again, as this was only implemented until roughly the end of 2019 (around the first half of 2020), its forecasting has compared favorably well against actuals moving forward after 2019 relative to the standalone baseline model plotted in Figure 6 below. The historical data shows a rather dramatic price jump that seems to be above 300 units, further escalating the volatility level over subsequent years. Finally, the hybrid model forecasts, plotted with a red line, exhibit more robust capacities for catching up with the overall pattern of trend and volatility in actual prices relative to the more volatile yet less responsive baseline Holt-Winters forecast shown before. This indicates that the GRU component has better boosted the ability of the model to capture more complex patterns of price movements, especially relating to higher volatility times. The closer alignment between actual and predicted values at the forecast period indicates that a hybrid approach is more suitable for capturing long-term trends and short-term fluctuations in rice prices.

Figure 7. Holt-Winters GRU Hybrid Model Rice Price Forecast

One of the significant advantages that hybrid models bring is higher accuracy in grasping complicated patterns in time series. Traditional models like Holt-Winters are suited for linear relationships but find it challenging to deal with nonlinear trends, which prevail in the case of most agricultural commodities. Thus, Hybrid models can adjust to nonlinearities by combining machine learning algorithms like artificial neural networks (ANNs), improving the quality of their forecasts. For instance, it was tested with a model that included cluster algorithms and used a multilayer perception network. This hybrid system significantly improved compared to other benchmark models because of the predicted world rice price. Crops are inherently seasonal or at least subjected to the cycles of planting and harvest, weather events, and the general movement of the global marketplace. The decomposition of time series and machine learning algorithms allow these models to separate noise with the perfection of ranking seasonal components. This is highly beneficial to stakeholders like farmers and policymakers, who are very dependent on precise forecasting ability to make production and market strategy decisions.

Hybrid models are reliable in forecasting, thus affecting the decisions of farmers, marketers, and policymakers. Stakeholders could adjust activities according to the forecast given. For example, knowing that prices may go up should motivate farmers to sell at the best time or advise governments to stock up on supplies in expectation of a shortage.

The hybrid models represent a further step into forecasting the seasonality of rice prices. They merge the best of old statistical methods with the current best practices of modern machine learning techniques. Hybrid models, with their ability to increase accuracy, capture complicated seasonal patterns, adaptability to the limitation in the data available, and provide insight into crucial decision-making processes, prove valuable tools for agricultural activities. Rice markets continue gaining ground toward globalization, subjecting them to a flood of pressures. Such advanced forecasting methods require effective utilization for food security and economic stability.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The comprehensive analysis of rice price forecasting using the Holt-Winters-GRU hybrid model demonstrates significant advantages in both accuracy and interpretability. Superior performance was also shown in the test RMSE of 27.7532 and a minimal training-test performance gap of 0.0695, which proves strong predictive capability for rice price movements. This architecture has successfully brought the power of traditional statistical methods (Holt-Winters) and advanced deep learning (GRU) together. This was seen through weight heatmap analysis, showing sophisticated pattern recognition capabilities across different temporal scales. Its ability to capture dramatic 2008 price spiking and market stabilization periods afterward suggests effectiveness in extreme events and expected market conditions. The network architecture has 128 GRU units and 151,301 total parameters. It should, therefore, be capable of capturing the multiple-sided nature of rice price dynamics with generalization capability intact. These results suggest that hybrid Holt-Winters-GRU models could potentially be precious tools for policymakers, traders, and market analysts in forecasting rice prices, considering their ability to absorb seasonal patterns and market shock movements. The success of this model suggests that such hybrid approaches might also help analyze any other prices of agricultural commodities whose patterns exhibit similar patterns of combinations of seasonality and market-driven volatility.

The proposed hybrid Holt-Winters-GRU model seems promising for forecasting seasonal agricultural product prices. To have a more significant impact, it must be used as a real-time forecasting tool, with periodic retraining, and supported by an alert system during critical price movements. Further extension can be made by including external factors and looking into ensemble methods to enhance its predictive power. Besides, this model can be applied in risk

management, policy analysis, and scenario planning. Future research areas include further application of the model in other commodities, investigation of its performance in various conditions of the economy, and advanced techniques like transfer learning. With such recommendations, the hybrid model will enhance informed decision-making in agriculture.

Acknowledgment

The researchers thank the Research and Publication Center (RPC) and the Administration for extending financial assistance and their colleagues' moral support.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Alvarez, S. C., Jacoba, F., Antonio, O. C. C., Gabriel, A. G., & Herezo, M. C. (2022). Food sufficiency, tariffication policy, and business strategy: A new business model for the rice milling industry in the Philippines. *MEC-J (Management and Economics Journal)*, 6(2), 109-128. <https://doi.org/10.18860/mec-j.v6i2.17020>
- Ananda, M. I. (2023). Model Analysis of Gated Recurrent Unit for Multivariate Rice Price Forecasting. *Jurnal ELTIKOM: Jurnal Teknik Elektro, Teknologi Informasi dan Komputer*, 7(2), 125-132. <https://doi.org/10.31961/eltikom.v7i2.770>
- Archontoulis, S. V., & Miguez, F. E. (2015). Nonlinear regression models and applications in agricultural research. *Agronomy Journal*, 107(2), 786-798. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj2012.0506>
- Chandra, N., Ahuja, L., Khatri, S. K., & Monga, H. (2021). Utilizing gated recurrent units to retain long term dependencies with recurrent neural network in text classification. *J. Inf. Syst. Telecommun*, 2, 89.
- Feng, P., Wang, B., Li Liu, D., Waters, C., Xiao, D., Shi, L., & Yu, Q. (2020). Dynamic wheat yield forecasts are improved by a hybrid approach using a biophysical model and machine learning technique. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 285, 107922. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2020.107922>
- Gamberini, R., Lolli, F., Rimini, B., & Sgarbossa, F. (2010). Forecasting of sporadic demand patterns with seasonality and trend components: an empirical comparison between Holt-Winters and (S) ARIMA methods. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, Article-ID. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2010/579010>
- Grzegorzczuk, M., Mariniello, M., Nurski, L., & Schraepen, T. (2021). *Blending the physical and virtual: a hybrid model for the future of work* (No. 14/2021). Bruegel Policy Contribution.
- Harahap, A., Fathoni, M., & Sumardi, H. (2023, March). Prediction Farmer Exchange Rate Comparative Method of Analysis Holth-Winters Smoothing and Seasonal ARIMA. In *Mathematics and Science Education International Seminar 2021 (MASEIS 2021)* (pp. 107-116). Atlantis Press. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-012-1_15
- He, X., Zhao, W., Gao, Z., Zhang, Q., & Wang, W. (2024). A hybrid prediction interval model for short-term electric load forecast using Holt-Winters and Gate Recurrent Unit. *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 38, 101343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2024.101343>

High Rice Prices Worldwide Likely to Continue Into 2024. (2023, December 26). Voice of America. <https://www.voanews.com/a/hold-for-holidays-high-rice-prices-worldwide-likely-to-continue-into-2024/7403691.html>

Jin, X. B., Yang, N. X., Wang, X. Y., Bai, Y. T., Su, T. L., & Kong, J. L. (2020). Hybrid deep learning predictor for smart agriculture sensing based on empirical mode decomposition and gated recurrent unit group model. *Sensors*, 20(5), 1334.

Khodadadi, N., Towfek, S. K., Zaki, A. M., Alharbi, A. H., Khodadadi, E., Khafaga, D. S., ... & Eid, M. M. (2024). Predicting normalized difference vegetation index using a deep attention network with bidirectional GRU: a hybrid parametric optimization approach. *International Journal of Data Science and Analytics*, 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41060-024-00640-8>

Kundu, R., & Sharma, A. (2022). Development of Seasonal ARIMA Model to Predict Wholesale Price of Rice in Delhi Market. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 41(48), 155-161.

Laiprakobsup, T. (2019). The policy effect of government assistance on the rice production in Southeast Asia: Comparative case studies of Thailand, Vietnam, and the Philippines. *Development Studies Research*, 6(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21665095.2019.1568900>

Lima, S., Gonçalves, A. M., & Costa, M. (2019, December). Time series forecasting using Holt-Winters exponential smoothing: An application to economic data. In *AIP conference proceedings* (Vol. 2186, No. 1). AIP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5137999>

Liu, Y., Yang, C., Huang, K., & Liu, W. (2023). A Multi-Factor Selection and Fusion Method through the CNN-LSTM Network for Dynamic Price Forecasting. *Mathematics*, 11(5), 1132.

Liu, C., Sun, B., Zhang, C., & Li, F. (2020). A hybrid prediction model for residential electricity consumption using holt-winters and extreme learning machine. *Applied energy*, 275, 115383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115383>

Macia, S., Macuacua, J., Vilanculos, A., & Mahaluça, F. (2024). Demand of Imported Rice in Mozambique (2011-2020). *American Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 10(1), 142-159.

Montano, V. E., & Bulao, M. T. S. Random Forest Analysis of Exogenous Variables Impacting Rice Production in the Philippines

Newclick Dijital Reklam Ajansi. (2024). *Global rice prices to stay hot until 2025, warns World Bank*. Millermagazine.com. <https://millermagazine.com/blog/global-rice-prices-to-stay-hot-until-2025-warns-world-bank-5467>

Ni'mah, R. (2023). Structural Time Series Model using Hamiltonian Monte Carlo for Rice Price. *Engineering, Mathematics and Computer Science Journal (EMACS)*, 5(3), 103-109.

Redych, O., & Boichuk, R. (2024). Comparative Analysis of Holt-Winters Algorithms on the Oracle Machine Learning Platform. *Applied Innovations in IT*, 71.

Rusman, M. A. A., & Antriyandarti, E. (2024). Analysis of production projections and factors that correlated with rice production in Indonesia. *AGROMIX*, 15(1), 82-89. <https://doi.org/10.35891/agx.v15i1.4061>

Septiana, D. (2024). Forecasting Rice Prices with Holt-Winter Exponential Smoothing Model. *Hanif Journal of Information Systems*, 1(2), 62-67. <https://doi.org/10.56211/hanif.v1i2.17>

Somasundaram, A., & Reddy, U. S. (2017, June). Modelling a stable classifier for handling large scale data with noise and imbalance. In *2017 International Conference on Computational Intelligence in Data Science (ICCIDS)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIDS.2017.8272643>

- Sudheer, G., & Suseelatha, A. (2015). Short term load forecasting using wavelet transform combined with Holt–Winters and weighted nearest neighbor models. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 64, 340-346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2014.07.043>
- Sun, F., Meng, X., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Jiang, H., & Liu, P. (2023). Agricultural Product Price Forecasting Methods: A Review. *Agriculture*, 13(9), 1671. <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-0472/13/9/1671#>
- Trnka, M., Hlavinka, P., Možný, M., Semerádová, D., Štěpánek, P., Balek, J., ... & Zalud, Z. (2020). Czech Drought Monitor System for monitoring and forecasting of agricultural drought and drought impacts.
- Trull, O., García-Díaz, J. C., & Troncoso, A. (2020). Initialization methods for multiple seasonal Holt–Winters forecasting models. *Mathematics*, 8(2), 268. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math8020268>
- Wang, L., Feng, J., Sui, X., Chu, X., & Mu, W. (2020). Agricultural product price forecasting methods: research advances and trend. *British Food Journal*, 122(7), 2121-2138. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-09-2019-0683>
- Wang, J., Wang, Z., Li, X., & Zhou, H. (2022). Artificial bee colony-based combination approach to forecasting agricultural commodity prices. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 38(1), 21-34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2019.08.006>
- Widayanti, S., Rachmah, M., Yektiningsih, E., & Setiawan, R. F. (2022). The Impact of Rice Import Policy on Community Economic Welfare in East Java. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 5(01), 106-110. DOI: 10.47191/jefms/v5-i1-13
- Wei, Y., Chen, S., Ye, S., Han, B., & Gong, C. (2024). Robust Learning under Hybrid Noise. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.04029*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.04029>
- Xiong, T., Li, C., & Bao, Y. (2018). Seasonal forecasting of agricultural commodity price using a hybrid STL and ELM method: Evidence from the vegetable market in China. *Neurocomputing*, 275, 2831-2844. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2017.11.053>
- Zhang, L., Wang, B., Yuan, X., & Liang, P. (2022). Remaining useful life prediction via improved CNN, GRU and residual attention mechanism with soft thresholding. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 22(15), 15178-15190.

